

BASICS OF ELECTRON-OPTICAL SURVEILLANCE WITH UAVS

Nabiyev R.

Doctor of Techn. Science, Professor

National Aviation Academy of Azerbaijan (Baku)

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1727-0360>

Abdullayev A.

Cand. of phys.-math. sc.

Doctorate of National Aviation Academy of Azerbaijan (Baku)

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7672-3940>

Abstract

The article presents a final analysis of the conditions for using unmanned aerial vehicles and the results obtained from their application in successfully completing tasks related to search and rescue operations, as well as the observation of strategic objects. The importance of applying advanced technologies in responding swiftly during emergencies, the activities of the team, and determining deployment positions has been substantiated, emphasizing and highlighting the necessity of using unmanned aerial vehicles. It is researched hereby, how unmanned aerial vehicles operate in complex and challenging conditions through the application of technological innovations based on the current operational task. It has been highlighted that the currently available multicopter, glider, and VTOL-based unmanned aerial vehicles, categorized by weight and size as nano, micro, mini, small, medium, and large, are utilized as primary and auxiliary elements for the digitalization of the integrated use of forces and resources during various international and local search-and-rescue missions, as well as other special tasks and for the integration of the process with artificial intelligence solution. It has been noted that this also plays an important role in the successful completion of the intended operation. The article also mentions that drones are widely used in aerial reconnaissance and search and rescue missions, in delivering medicines and essential goods to provide medical assistance to the required point within flight restrictions, as well as in monitoring the territory in emergency situations.

Keywords: Unmanned aerial vehicles, surveillance, optimization, electro-optical camera, artificial intelligence.

1. Introduction

In situations where human observation is not possible or is difficult, the ability to monitor an area using unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) equipped with an electro-optical payload (EOP) and the ability to transmit the video over long distances have given these types of aircraft significant advantages [1-3].

The development of information reception, processing, and transmission, as well as digital and artificial intelligence technologies, has significantly improved the quality, transmission speed, and volume of images, leading to their ability to be transmitted over greater distances.

However, digital technologies have their own shortcomings, which affect their effectiveness in reconnaissance and surveillance systems.

The electro-optical systems installed on UAVs are primarily used for the following purposes:

- Conducting aerial electronic-optical reconnaissance (surveillance) and transmitting images to the control center in the real time in order to monitor operational conditions in an area of interest;
- Obtaining detailed video images of the object or area of interest, as well as the area, field and objects where the patrol-surveillance flight is being conducted;
- For the purposes of obtaining photo or video images of objects located in the area that are not visually observable by the human eye, range finding to the target, and providing laser guidance (designation).

Technically, the EOPs (electro-optical payloads) are either directly installed on the airframe of the aircraft through their own design as a single system, or via

a gyroscopically stabilized (gyrostable) adjustable platform. This gyrostable system ensures that the EOP (electro-optical payload) can rotate and be controlled in any direction at the given speed. The stable connection between the aircraft's structure and the Y-axis of the payload, along with the ability to rotate 360°, creates the basis for obtaining stable and high-quality high-resolution photo and video images [4-6].

The camera and electro-optical devices are primarily used for obtaining images of the front or other surroundings of the aircraft from a distance. For this purpose, during the flight planning, in addition to meteorological limitations, the flight altitude, air humidity, viewing angle, and azimuth must be taken into account. Additionally, depending on the season, the angle of sunlight during the shooting time and the rotation of the payload in the direction of the aircraft's wheels must be closely monitored [7, 8].

The application of optical devices allows solving many issues. It is known that the weight and cost of such devices increase depending on the distance to the target and the quality (high resolution) of the obtained image of the observed area. To obtain quality results, strict technical requirements must be met to stabilize the aircraft's position during the shooting period in the air. Non-stable optical systems support the target "tracking" and observation mode at a low level. When attempting to apply this mode, many limitations and difficulties occur. Optical devices installed on gyrostable platforms are more efficient. Sufficient practical experience has been accumulated by specialists in the application of these types of devices [9, 10].

Optical devices with gyrostable platforms ensure the tracking of selected targets, both stationary and moving, during flight. The integration of daytime (TV), thermal, and infrared (IR) cameras into a single platform results in obtaining of high-information-content image. This also ensures the processing of the image obtained in video and photo formats, converting it into an analog or digital signal. It also provides the ability to accurately determine the coordinates of the target through laser rangefinder technology on a gyrostable platform. Additionally, if the EOP is integrated with a laser designator for guiding laser-targeted missiles and bombs, using a laser generator (energy source), it increases its weight, cost, and efficiency [11].

Purpose of the work – The optimization of electronic-optical surveillance with unmanned aerial vehicles.

2. Resolution capabilities of electronic-optical systems.

By the resolution capability of a digital electronic-optical system, it is meant the ability to form the level of detail in the images of objects located at a given distance from the system's camera lens. The main factor

Figure 1. The field of view created by the lens of the electro-optical system

$$\delta = \frac{l}{R_{yer}} \gg 0.0003 \quad (1)$$

Here, l is the length equal to the largest linear dimension of the observed area, and R_{yer} is the average radius of the area. Due to the inclination of the Earth's surface, the curves (mountains and valleys) present there are considered as planar in the calculations. Thus, the effectiveness of the application of the electro-optical system is strongly influenced by the fact that the real appearance of the Earth's surface does not have a planar structure. The EOP on the UAV is intended to perform

determining the resolution capability of electronic-optical systems is the CCD (charge-coupled device) matrix, which projects the image obtained after passing through the lens [12-15].

The source of the image data is the Earth's surface or the airspace. The field of view angle of the lens determines the volume of the information. The images captured from the Earth's surface and airspace strongly influence the resolution factor of the system. It should be considered that the image displayed on the screen changes depending on the physical composition and color of the observed area, as well as the difference between the screen image of objects on the Earth's surface and their real line measurements. Figure 1 describes the field of view formed by the lens of the electronic-optical system. The dimensions of the field of view depend on the UAV's flight altitude, the lens's view angle, and the inclination angle of the lens's optical axis [16].

It can be seen from fig. 1 that the shape of the observed area is geometrically close to a trapezoid. In the initial approach of the calculations, the possibility of low correlation can be used.

specific functions. Therefore, the evaluation of EOPs is based on the capabilities of UAV applications, such as detecting and tracking typical objects, measuring the resolution of the obtained image, and other related factors [17- 20].

One of the key parameters that allows determining the required flight altitude, depending on the capabilities of the electro-optical system installed on the UAV, is the fill factor (Figure 2):

$$K_{doldurma} = \frac{F_{h\delta def}}{F} \quad (2)$$

$F_{h\delta def}$ – the area of the target visible region, F – the area of the observation (surveillance) region.

Figure 2. The graph of the fill factor dependence on flight altitude

The fill factor is the quantity that indicates how many times the required field of view must be enlarged for the selected object (target) to be visible and tracked on the observation monitor [21- 25].

The size of the CCD matrix significantly affects the resolution of the image obtained through the electro-optical device. Thus, the size of the CCD matrix determines the sampling level of the image coming from the optical lens. The larger the size of the matrix, the higher the sampling level and the greater the detail of the image on the system's screen. To obtain a new high-resolution image with a digital electro-optical system close to the optical resolution capability of the lens, it is necessary to either have a very

large-sized CCD matrix or reduce the viewing angle. The resolution capability of a digital electro-optical system (lens - CCD matrix - screen) is determined based on a set of parameters, depending on the ability to magnify the image on the screen.

$$R = f(L, \beta, \gamma, \varphi, M) \quad (3)$$

Here: L – the inclined (slanted) distance to a point on the Earth's surface, (β, γ, φ) – the angular changes of the observed point in relation to the optical axis (left-right, up-down), and the tilt angle of the optical axis in the normal coordinate system, M – the size of the CCD matrix [26, 27].

To evaluate the resolution capability of a digital electro-optical system, images of objects characteristic for search operations can be used via the UAV. The demonstration of the resolution capabilities of the electro-optical system can be considered by reviewing the corresponding graphic projection of a "Human" object as an example. The dimensions of the projection have been adjusted to match the projection of the matrix and are shown as the corresponding surface. Depending on the size of the projection, the element can have dimensions of millimeters, centimeters, and meters of the CCD matrix, depending on the number of "pixels" (dots). For this reason, when the "Human" target is zoomed in to the maximum, it is possible to see as many dots as the resolution allows [28].

3. Conclusion

1. The presence of the most advanced electro-optical system on an unmanned aerial vehicle does not guarantee its successful practical application and high efficiency;

2. The use of nano, micro, and mini-sized unmanned aerial vehicles is not considered appropriate for the execution of surveillance, search, and reconnaissance tasks over large areas;

3. When surveillance is conducted using an unmanned aerial vehicle on a target with pre-known coordinates, the probability of achieving a successful result is high.

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